

D2.2 Production and quality assurance of samples for machining and surface characterization

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Deliverable Information sheet

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Executive summary

Additive Manufacturing (AM) is a transformative technology that integrates material creation with part manufacturing, enabling intricate geometries and functional components to be produced with minimal waste. However, achieving the required surface integrity and mechanical properties for industrial applications often demands additional post-processing steps, such as machining and heat treatments. The SuPreAM project focuses on optimizing these processes for steel components, targeting two industrial applications: aerospace components and injection moulding parts. The overarching goal is to reduce manufacturing costs by minimizing scrap and reprocessing while enhancing surface quality and performance.

This deliverable corresponds to Work Package 2 (WP2), titled Definition of requirements, AM materials, and process-chain implementation. WP2 establishes the engineering foundation necessary for producing industrial parts by defining requirements and selecting manufacturing processes, materials, and post-treatments to meet those requirements. AM presents a unique challenge because the material and part geometry are created simultaneously, unlike conventional manufacturing where material properties are predefined. This fusion of steps in AM necessitates careful consideration of the process parameters to ensure the part achieves the desired properties across its entirety. This deliverable involves the analysis of requirements for the two selected applications, followed by the selection of suitable AM technologies and materials. A comprehensive evaluation was conducted, including material characterization, parameter optimization, assessment of microstructural behaviour, the influence of shape and orientation, heat treatments, and anisotropy of properties. Additionally, the design and production of test samples for advanced characterization and machining trials were completed during this phase.

The primary role of this deliverable is to guarantee the optimal selection of materials and processes tailored to the requirements of each application. It focuses on optimizing manufacturing and heat treatment parameters to achieve target properties and defines and manufacture the necessary samples for testing and validation in subsequent work packages. These steps are crucial for generating realistic samples that address the engineering challenges of AM and support the development of predictive simulation models for finishing operations. Without this groundwork, achieving the project's objectives—such as minimizing scrap, reducing reprocessing loops, and improving surface integrity—would not be feasible.

Positioned at the beginning of the technical work plan, this deliverable establishes the foundation for manufacturing samples used in machining tests, advanced characterizations, and simulation fitting throughout the project. The methodological approach relied on a cascade decision-making process, where materials, processes, parameters, and heat treatments were evaluated iteratively to identify optimal candidates based on technical and performance criteria.

Figure 1. Project workflow.

The main results highlight two tailored solutions for the selected applications. For aerospace components, Laser Wire Directed Energy Deposition (DED) was identified as the optimal technology due to its scalability, cost-effective wire feedstock, and reliability. The material selected was PH17-4 stainless steel, which demonstrated superior toughness and reduced property heterogeneity after a custom heat treatment. This treatment ensured uniform mechanical properties across different geometries, achieving optimal performance compared to conventional counterparts.

Figure 2. Sample of different wall shapes manufactured by Laser Wire DED technology.

For injection moulding, Laser Powder Bed Fusion (L-PBF) was the predefined technology, and a MS1 Maraging steel was selected due to the strong wear resistance, good valance of corrosion resistant and elevated toughness at the working conditions. A custom-designed heat treatment minimized dimensional distortion and reduced costs while achieving target properties. Furthermore, a cobalt-free Maraging steel, patented by ArcelorMittal, was evaluated and will be included in final demonstrator tests to benchmark its performance against MS1. For this application, optimizations in part positioning, raw material quality assurance, and process parameters were also implemented to ensure an optimum AM process.

Figure 3. Samples of MS1 Lean-Si produced by L-PBF technology.

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Terminology and Acronyms

AB	As-Built
AM	Additive Manufacturing
CT	Computed tomography
DED	Directed Energy Deposition
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
HT	Heat Treatment
L-PBF	Lase Powder Bed Fusion
MW	Massive Wall
SMW	Super Massive Wall
SPT	Small Punch Test
SW	Single Wall
UTS	Ultimate Tensile Strength
WP	Work Package
YS	Yield Stress

1. Introduction

This deliverable provides a comprehensive overview of the activities carried out in Work Package 2 (WP2), titled Definition of Requirements, AM Materials, and Process-Chain Implementation. WP2 is critical to establishing the foundation for the SuPreAM project, as it ensures that the materials, additive manufacturing (AM) processes, and post-processing treatments are tailored to meet the specific requirements of the selected industrial applications. The overarching objective of this deliverable is to guarantee that all printed materials—whether sample parts or final demonstrators—fulfil the defined properties necessary for successful machining, finishing, and performance evaluation.

The work is structured into four key tasks: (1) defining requirements and selecting materials and AM technologies for two representative case studies (injection moulding and aerospace components); (2) implementing the necessary AM processes to achieve the desired material properties, including parameter tuning for Laser Powder Bed Fusion (L-PBF) and Directed Energy Deposition (DED); (3) designing and producing 3D-printed samples for characterization, machining, and validation in subsequent work packages; and (4) conducting quality assurance to ensure compliance with requirements. This structured approach enables the evaluation and optimization of process parameters, material behaviour, and heat treatments while addressing challenges such as anisotropy, surface integrity, and microstructural defects.

The deliverable not only establishes the engineering foundation for the SuPreAM project but also ensures that the samples and technologies developed during WP2 are aligned with the broader project objectives. These efforts are essential for minimizing scrap, reducing reprocessing, and enhancing the quality and performance of AM components.

1.1 Objectives of the deliverable

The main objectives of this deliverable are.

- Define and validate requirements for materials, AM processes, and post-processing strategies to produce steel components for aerospace and injection moulding applications.
- Select materials and AM technologies that meet industrial demands, focusing on scalability and optimization.
- Establish methodologies for tuning AM parameters, heat treatments, and material characterization.
- Produce high-quality AM samples to represent the target applications accurately.
- Minimize defects, improve surface integrity, and enhance the homogeneity of mechanical properties in AMed components.
- Address challenges such as anisotropy, defects, and material transitions in hybrid manufacturing processes.
- Optimize the full process chain from raw material selection to post-processing.

1.2 Structure of the deliverable

The deliverable has been structured as follows:

1. Definition of Requirements, AM Parts, and Material Selection:
 - i. Definition of the minimum requirements for aerospace and injection moulding applications.
 - ii. Description of the selected materials and AM technologies.
2. Additive Manufacturing Technology Implementation:
 - i. Develop and optimize AM process parameters for L-PBF, DED, and hybrid manufacturing.
3. Design and production of 3D printed samples:
 - i. Definition of the samples
 - ii. Manufacturing of the samples
4. Quality assurance of samples and heat treatment:
 - i. Design of the optimal heat treatments
 - ii. Classification of typical defects

2. Content

2.1 Definition of Requirements, AM Parts, and Material Selection

In this section, the requirements for aerospace and injection moulding application sample parts are defined, focusing on functional, mechanical, and surface integrity demands. It also outlines the rationale behind material and AM technology selection, including the availability of materials in the required format for each technology.

2.1.1 Definition of the minimum requirements for aerospace and injection moulding applications

The company DRT (for the injection mould application) and SGC (for the aerospace application) have defined the requirements for both of the components proposed based on the materials properties of the conventional materials and technologies applied for the original components. The following tables shown the definition of requirements:

Definition of the requirements for the injection mould [DRT]	
Material selected for the application	MS1 & MS1 Lean-Si
Yield Strength (MPa)	2080
UTS (MPa)	2000
Elongation (%)	4
Hardness (HRC)	50-57
Roughness	VDI = 0 → Ra = 0.025 (for high gloss reflective finish)
	VDI = 0 → Ra = 0.05 (for shining finish)
	VDI = 30 → Ra = 3.2 (normal polishing - medium)
	VDI = 42 → Ra = 12.5 (normal polishing - rough)

Table 1. Requirements for Injection Mould application.

Definition of the requirements for the aerospace component [SGC]	
Original material employed for the application	PH13-8 Stainless Steel
Material selected for the application	PH17-4 Stainless Steel
Yield Strength (MPa)	1138
UTS (MPa)	1207
Elongation (%)	12
Hardness (HRC)	35-45
Roughness (Ra)	1.6 & 0.8 (Defined in technical drawing)
Impact toughness (J) at -50°C	>32

Table 2. Requirements for Aerospace component application.

As basic consideration for the injection mould component, the critical requirements are based on wear resistance (related with high hardness of the material), medium to good corrosion resistance, microstructural stability at operation temperatures and good toughness resistance. For the aerospace application on the other hand, the main performance requirements are related to a good mechanical resistance, corrosion resistance and sufficient impact toughness at operation temperatures (around -50°C).

While the requirements presented in the tables outline the baseline for material properties based on conventional technologies and components, they do not represent strict engineering minimums for both components. Additive manufacturing (AM) provides unique advantages, such as design freedom, which can compensate for potential reductions in certain material properties. For instance, enhanced cooling efficiency achieved through optimized conformal cooling channels in injection moulds can lower operating temperatures, reducing the overall material demands. Similarly, the ability to strategically add material where needed and reduce weight by removing material in low-stress areas allows for greater flexibility in meeting performance requirements for aerospace components while optimizing component design.

2.1.2 Description of the selected materials and AM technologies

For the injection mould application, two materials were selected: MS1, a Maraging steel known for its excellent mechanical properties, superior wear resistance due to its high hardness, and a good balance of corrosion resistance. Additionally, a novel material, Lean-Si MS1, patented by ArcelorMittal, has been tested within this project. This material is based on the commercial MS1 but avoids the use of cobalt, addressing issues of cost, toxicity, and its classification as a critical raw material. The absence of cobalt is compensated through adjustments in the alloy composition to achieve performance close to the original MS1. The L-PBF (Laser Powder Bed Fusion) technology was selected for this application, as DRT already possesses an L-PBF machine, although with limited experience using these materials.

For the aerospace application, the original component was produced by mechanical milling from a block of PH13-8 stainless steel. Two additive manufacturing technologies were evaluated for this application: Laser Wire DED (Directed Energy Deposition) and L-PBF, based on the part's characteristics. The material chosen was PH17-4 stainless steel, which is available in the required formats—wire for DED and powder for L-PBF. PH17-4 is a precipitation-hardening stainless steel with excellent mechanical properties, slightly lower than those of PH13-8 but offering improved corrosion resistance. Additive manufacturing processes often enhance mechanical performance due to rapid cooling, leading to refined microstructures and better grain control. This advantage was a key consideration in the selection of both the material and the manufacturing technologies for this application.

2.2 Additive Manufacturing Technology Implementation

This section focuses on the development and optimization of additive manufacturing process parameters for the selected technologies—L-PBF and Laser Wire DED. The goal is to achieve the desired mechanical properties and evaluate the technical challenges for the chosen materials and applications. Emphasis is placed on tuning process parameters to align with the specific requirements of aerospace and injection moulding components, while ensuring the reproducibility and reliability of the manufacturing process.

2.2.1 Develop and optimize AM process parameters for L-PBF, DED, and hybrid manufacturing

The optimization of additive manufacturing (AM) process parameters began with a clear definition of the specific needs for both applications—an injection mould and an aerospace component. These optimization needs are summarized in the following tables:

DRT - Injection mould	
Material / Technology	Need optimization?
MS1 / L-PBF	No [Comercial material & parameters]
MS1 Lean-Si / L-PBF	Yes [Material & parameters]

Table 3. Injection mould application.

SGC - Aerospace component	
Material / Technology	Need optimization?
PH17-4 / DED	Yes [Material & parameters]
PH17-4 / L-PBF	No [Comercial material & parameters]
PH13-8 / Conventional	No [Comercial material & parameters]

Table 4. Aerospace component application.

For the injection mould application using the MS1 material and L-PBF technology, no significant implementation efforts were necessary. MS1 is a commercially available material and is already included in the machine parameters database of DRT's L-PBF equipment. As a result, sample production with this material was straightforward.

However, the process for MS1 Lean-Si, a new material developed and patented by ArcelorMittal, required technology implementation efforts. The optimization process involved two main steps:

- Minimizing porosity: This step focused on ensuring high-density parts by addressing potential gas entrapment during either powder production or the additive process itself.
- Optimizing the microstructure: Following mechanical characterization, this step aimed to improve the material's performance through suitable heat treatments.

Figure 4. MS1 Lean-Si part produced by L-PBF.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 5 Microstructural analysis of MS1 Lean-Si samples. (a) Polished state magnification x50, (b) magnification x100, (c) magnification x100, (d) magnification x200, and (e) magnification x400. Micrograph (b) to (e) etched with Vilella's reagent.

Preliminary tests revealed the presence of spherical porosity in MS1 Lean-Si samples, likely caused by gas entrapment. Microstructural analysis showed a tempered martensitic structure, with no significant differences observed between the two heat treatment (HT) conditions applied by ArcelorMittal.

Subsequently, 12 tensile specimens were produced from the two HT conditions in both vertical and horizontal build orientations. Of these, 10 samples failed prematurely during testing, either breaking outside the gauge length or at the grips, yielding no reliable data. The remaining two samples exhibited brittle behaviour, suggesting critical issues with ductility.

MS1 Lean-Si Trial 1			
Sample	Yield Strength (MPa)	UTS (MPa)	Elongation (%)
T2 (HT1) Vertical	1659	1719	2.6
T5 (HT2) Horizontal	1484	1577	0.3

Table 5. MS1 Lean-Si tensile test results of trial 1 [ASTM E8]

Following these results, ArcelorMittal conducted a new evaluation of the raw material and applied a proprietary heat treatment. A second round of testing was performed with three vertical samples, which again demonstrated brittle behaviour. Given these findings, further independent investigations are needed to address the brittleness issue. As a result, the project proceeded with conventional MS1 material for the injection mould application.

MS1 Lean-Si Trial 2			
Sample	Yield Strength (MPa)	UTS (MPa)	Elongation (%)
T49 Vertical	1558	1604	0.9
T50 Vertical	1572	1596	1.1
T51 Vertical	1541	1592	1.3

Table 6. MS1 Lean-Si tensile test results of trial 2 [ASTM E8]

Figure 6. MS1 Lean-Si tensile test specimens after testing showing a failure mode out of the calibrated zone.

Despite the setbacks, MS1 Lean-Si remains a promising alternative due to its cobalt-free composition, which offers significant economic and environmental benefits. Once the material's ductility issues are resolved, it will be reintroduced for evaluation in future injection mould applications, as DRT has expressed strong interest in its potential.

For the aerospace application, PH17-4 material was selected for implementation via Laser Wire DED technology. Unlike the injection mould application, the optimization effort focused solely on this manufacturing route, as the material was already available in wire form.

The standard approach for implementing new materials in Laser Wire DED involves three key stages:

- Single-track deposition: Parameters such as wire feed rate, laser power, deposition path, and standoff distance are optimized to achieve proper penetration and track geometry.
- Single-wall fabrication: Optimization of walls consisting of one track per layer to ensure consistency in geometry and mechanical properties.
- Massive-wall fabrication: Optimization of multi-track walls for building bulkier structures, which are essential for manufacturing complex parts and hybrid components.

Figure 7. Production of PH17-4 samples with Laser Wire DED technology.

After iterative adjustments, optimal deposition parameters were identified, enabling the production of three types of walls: Single Wall (SW), Massive Wall (MW), and Super Massive Wall (SMW). These walls were subjected to metallographic characterization, mechanical testing, and computed tomography analysis.

Figure 8. (Left) CT scan of one the PH17-4 MW.

Tensile testing was conducted on samples extracted from the walls, with results summarized in the table below. The testing scheme included both 25 mm and 10 mm gauge lengths, with mean values reported for each wall type.

Single Wall (SW)

Massive Wall (MW)

Super Massive Wall (SMW)

Figure 9. Scheme for the sample extraction in the different walls manufactured.

PH17-4 Laser Wire DED As-Built			
Single Wall			
Sample	Yield Strength (MPa)	UTS (MPa)	Elongation (%)
SW1779 (Lo=10 mm)	508	1016	16
SW1779 (Lo=25 mm)	473	1008	11
SW1782 (Lo=10 mm)	584	1054	16
SW1782 (Lo=25 mm)	505	1025	10
SW1787 (Lo=10 mm)	486	983	18
SW1787 (Lo=25 mm)	436	1008	11

Table 7. As-Built Single Wall (PH17-4).

PH17-4 Laser Wire DED As-Built			
Massive Wall			
Sample	Yield Strength (MPa)	UTS (MPa)	Elongation (%)
T1 MW1797 Vertical	965	1209	6
T2 MW1797 Vertical	982	1203	10
T3 MW1797 Vertical	957	1213	9
T1 MW1797 Horizontal	881	1152	17
T2 MW1797 Horizontal	737	1154	15
T3 MW1797 Horizontal	853	1089	17

Table 8. As-Built Massive Wall (PH17-4).

PH17-4 Laser Wire DED As-Built Super Massive Wall			
Sample	Yield Strength (MPa)	UTS (MPa)	Elongation (%)
T1 SMW1 Vertical	564	1162	--
T2 SMW1 Vertical	527	1146	17
T3 SMW1 Vertical	525	1138	18
T1 SMW1 Horizontal	543	1119	21
T2 SMW1 Horizontal	547	1133	21
T3 SMW1 Horizontal	526	1130	19

Table 9. As-Built Super Massive Wall (PH17-4)

The results revealed significant differences in mechanical properties between the wall types. MW exhibited the highest yield strength and overall performance, while SW and SMW displayed significantly lower yield strength. These observations highlight the impact of geometry on the final properties of components produced using Laser Wire DED.

To address these disparities, a custom heat treatment strategy is being developed to homogenize material properties across different geometries. This step is critical to ensuring reliable performance and reproducibility in aerospace components produced through Laser Wire DED.

Additionally, the interface between the deposited material and the build plate has been analysed metallographically to ensure good wettability during the implementation of the hybrid route. This hybrid behaviour, which is heavily influenced by the residual stresses and the final component configuration of both the conventional part and the additive manufacturing addition, will be further evaluated in WP6.

2.3 Design and production of 3D printed samples

The successful implementation of additive manufacturing (AM) processes requires not only the optimization of process parameters but also the careful design, production, and evaluation of representative samples. These samples serve as a critical link between material development, process validation, and as evaluation of the surface integrity and software simulations along the project.

2.3.1 Definition of the samples

The first step involved defining the types of samples required for testing, considering factors such as geometry, orientation, material properties, and the end-use test. Specific designs were tailored to meet the evaluation needs by each of the consortium participant requirements. In order to proceed with the definition of the samples, they were divided in two groups, a first one designated for basic characterization and a second for the advance characterization to be evaluated along the different work packages (WP):

Figure 10. Sample definition divided in 2 groups.

A table file has been shared, completed and discussed by all members of the consortium where different characteristics of each sample have been defined. The characteristics were the following ones:

- WP the sample belongs
- Type of test to be perform (Standard employ if considered)
- Material of the samples
- Application (Injection Mold or Aerospace Component)
- Dimensions/Geometry of the samples (technical drawings)
- Number of samples per condition
- Total number of samples per material and technology
- Heat treatment needed? (If advised for the material/technology)
- Partner in charge of performing the heat treatment
- Machining required (size before machining)
- Partner in charge of machining
- Partner in charge of manufacturing
- Partner in charge of testing
- Relevant notes

Next an example of part of the completed sample definition table is presented.

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N
WP	Group of test	Test	Material	Application	Dimensions/geometry of samples	Number of samples per condition	Total number of samples per material and technology	Heat treatment	Partner in charge of	Machining required (Done before machining)	Partner in charge of manufacturing	Partner in charge of machining	Partner in charge of testing
2	2.1.1	Micrographic analysis	MS1 (AISI 316 L) D20	Multi & Aero	10x10x10mm	1	1	No	IDO	No	AMM (MS1) Lash 14 + PH17.4		IDO
2	2.1.2	Heat treatment design (HTD)	MS1 (AISI 316 L) D20	Multi & Aero	10x10x10mm	1	4	No	IDO	No	AMM (MS1) Lash 14 + PH17.4 D20 + 1407(MA) + 100 (PH17.4) D20		IDO
4		Tensile test ASTM B897 (Reference 2)	MS1 (AISI 316 L) D20 + D20 (PH17.4) D20	Multi & Aero		3 Long / 3 Tens	3	Yes/No	IDO	Yes (Diam. Error + Long. Error)	AMM (MS1) Lash 14 + PH17.4 D20 + 1407(MA) + 100 (PH17.4) D20	IDO	IDO
5		Charpy V-notch test (Reference 3) (Reference 4)	MS1 (AISI 316 L) D20 + D20 (PH17.4) D20	Multi & Aero	10x10x25mm	3 Long / 3 Tens	3	Yes/No	IDO	Yes (22x22x25mm)	AMM (MS1) Lash 14 + PH17.4 D20 + 1407(MA) + 100 (PH17.4) D20	IDO	IDO

Figure 11. Example of the sample definition document share across the consortium.

2.3.2 Manufacturing of the samples

Once the designs were finalized, the samples were produced using optimized AM parameters. This step also included the basic characterization of materials and technology routes that did not require further implementation.

Figure 12. Interior view of L-PBF machine manufacturing MS1 material for injection mould application.

Injection Mold Application

For the injection mould application, the commercial MS1 Maraging steel was evaluated. The first tests focused on producing samples and assessing the hardness of the material in its as-built (AB) state, without any heat treatment. Hardness, as previously mentioned, is directly linked to the wear resistance of the material—a critical property for ensuring the durability of injection moulds.

Def. of Requirements T2.1	Commercial MS1 at AB state HRC (Rockwell C Scale) Hardness
50-57	36

Table 10. Hardness values for MS1 after manufacturing (AB) – ISO 6508.

Initial evaluations revealed that the AB state of the material was inadequate for the intended application. Consequently, to proceed with the remaining basic characterization—tensile tests and impact toughness evaluations—it became necessary to include a heat treatment design phase.

Aerospace Application

For the aerospace application, the basic characterization of PH17-4 stainless steel produced by laser wire DED technology was carried out during the implementation phase. Subsequently, a second technology, L-PBF, was employed to produce PH17-4 samples. Hardness, tensile tests, and impact toughness evaluations were performed for these samples as well.

Def. of Requirements T2.1	L-PBF PH17-4 at AB state HRC (Rockwell C Scale) Hardness
35-45	40

Table 11. Hardness values for PH17-4 produced by L-PBF after manufacturing (AB) – ISO 6508.

L-PBF PH17-4 at AB state			
Sample	Yield Strength (MPa)	UTS (MPa)	Elongation (%)
Def. of Requirements T2.1	1138	1207	12
T1 Vertical	674	1261	11
T2 Vertical	576	1261	10
T3 Vertical	590	1287	11
T1 Horizontal	703	1287	10
T2 Horizontal	651	1285	10
T3 Horizontal	653	1259	12

Table 12. Tensile test of PH17-4 produced by L-PBF after manufacturing (AB) – ASTM E8.

Sample	L-PBF PH17-4 at AB state Charpy Test (J) at -50°C
Def. of Requirements T2.1	>32
Vertical	10
Horizontal	11

Table 13. Impact toughness test of PH17-4 produced by L-PBF after manufacturing (AB) – ISO 148.

The results of the as-built PH17-4 produced via L-PBF indicated that the material's properties fell below the minimum requirements. As a result, heat treatment was applied to determine whether the desired values could be achieved.

Challenges in Sample Manufacturing for Additive Manufacturing Technologies

During this stage, a recurring challenge in the optimization of additive manufacturing processes became evident. Conventional manufacturing processes typically accommodate the production of standard-sized samples without issue. However, for additive manufacturing—especially those using powder as raw material—the production of such samples presents significant economic and logistical constraints.

For instance, manufacturing ASTM E8 subsize samples, commonly used for tensile testing, requires a total length of 100 mm per vertical sample. In machines with a build plate of 250x250 mm, this often necessitates 60–75 kg of steel powder, even when producing just a single sample weighing a few grams. This makes it challenging to efficiently explore different parameters, powder qualities, material states, or new compositions.

To address this, the Small Punch Test (SPT) has been proposed as a solution. SPT uses tiny samples, typically discs or squares measuring approximately 10x10x1 mm, and can serve as a cost-effective and time-saving alternative during the early stages of optimization. When properly calibrated, SPT provides valuable insights into material behavior. However, it also presents challenges, particularly the need for precise calibration to ensure results can be reliably translated into conventional mechanical properties.

Figure 13. Scheme of a small punch test (SPT).

Recognizing the importance of this test, efforts were initiated to calibrate it for the applications under consideration in this project. The initial steps focused on defining a sample preparation protocol specifically for additive manufacturing materials. These preliminary calibration efforts were conducted at Idonial facilities, and further investigation will continue throughout the project.

Figure 14. Calibration and setup of the SPT.

2.4 Quality assurance of samples

Ensuring the quality of the produced samples is a critical step in the process, as it directly affects the reliability and performance of the final components. This section details the efforts undertaken to enhance the properties of the samples through optimized heat treatments and the identification of typical defects associated with additive manufacturing.

2.4.1 Design of the optimal heat treatments

Heat treatments play a critical role in tailoring the mechanical and microstructural properties of metallic materials. For the samples produced in this project, designing optimal heat treatment cycles was essential to address the limitations observed in the as-built (AB) state.

At this stage of the project, for the injection mould application, heat treatment development will focus exclusively on the commercial MS1 alloy manufactured via L-PBF technology. This decision was made while ArcelorMittal works to resolve the brittleness issues previously observed in the MS1 Lean-Si alloy. For the aerospace application, both the PH17-4 stainless

steel manufactured via laser wire DED technology and the PH17-4 alloy produced via L-PBF will undergo heat treatment design processes.

It is worth noting that, as specified in the project proposal, the heat treatment design was initially planned to utilize the dilatometric technique to determine optimal times and temperatures. However, given Idonial's advanced capabilities in using CALPHAD-based simulation methods to accurately design heat treatments, the decision was made to adopt this approach instead. Using Thermo-Calc software, simulations were employed to calibrate the heat treatment parameters with greater precision, including temperature profiles and time durations. These simulated parameters were subsequently applied to physical samples, which were then tested to evaluate the effectiveness of the designed heat treatments.

Injection Mold Application

For the injection mould application, the commercial MS1 Maraging steel was subjected to three different heat treatments to compare its properties in the as-built (AB) state with the minimal requirements. This family of alloys is typically heat-treated using a two-step process (as recommended by the powder manufacturer), consisting of solution annealing followed by quenching and tempering. This process aims to achieve a martensitic microstructure with a well-distributed array of precipitates that enhance the material's mechanical properties while maintaining good toughness.

However, several challenges arise when applying this conventional approach. First, the high temperatures required for solution annealing (above the A3 temperature, typically exceeding 900°C) can lead to surface oxidation and decarburization unless performed in a vacuum or protective atmosphere, significantly increasing treatment costs. Additionally, this process can induce dimensional distortions due to the stresses generated and relieved during the treatment. Notably, the solution annealing step was originally developed for alloys produced via conventional manufacturing methods and was not specifically optimized for additively manufactured materials.

When considering the injection mould application and the unique characteristics of the L-PBF (Laser Powder Bed Fusion) technology, further concerns arise. This additive manufacturing process involves extremely high cooling rates—on the order of tens of thousands of degrees per second during solidification and cooling—which typically results in a refined grain structure compared to conventional processes. Applying solution annealing can lead to recrystallization, negating the mechanical benefits of the fine-grain microstructure inherent to the as-built state.

To address these challenges, thermodynamic simulations were performed using Thermo-Calc software to analyse phase stability and select the most suitable heat treatments for the MS1 alloy manufactured via L-PBF. Three heat treatment approaches were selected:

- A conventional solution annealing, quenching, and tempering cycle to simulate the standard industrial process.
- A modified approach omitting the solution annealing step, followed by a single tempering treatment with a specific duration.

- A second modified approach also skipping solution annealing, but with an alternative tempering duration to optimize performance.

The temperatures and durations for both the annealing and tempering steps were carefully calibrated based on the thermodynamic simulations to achieve the most appropriate properties for the intended injection mold application.

HT code	Heat treatment applied	MS1 HRC (Rockwell C Scale) Hardness
	Def. of Requirements T2.1	50-57
AB	AB (No heat treatment)	36
S+490/6	Solution annealing 940°C (2h) + Tempering 490°C (6h)	52
490/1.5	Tempering 490°C (1.5h)	51
490/6	Tempering 490°C (6h)	52

Table 14. Hardness values for MS1 under different heat treatment conditions – ISO 6508.

Observing the results, similar hardness results are obtained for all 3 of the proposed heat treatments, all achieving the minimum requirements defined. For the tensile and impact test the 2 heat treatments selected are the conventional solution annealing + tempering and the only tempering for 1.5h, as it was the more cost competitive one in the case in can achieve minimum properties. Both heat treatments were applied to horizontal and vertical samples and tensile and impact toughness test performed over the samples.

Heat treated MS1 Tensile test				
HT Code	Sample	Yield Strength (MPa)	UTS (MPa)	Elongation (%)
Def. of Requirements T2.1		2000	2080	4
S+490/6	T1 Vertical	1910	1971	2

S+490/6	T2 Vertical	1888	1937	2
S+490/6	T3 Vertical	1881	1933	2
S+490/6	T1 Horizontal	1889	1962	7
S+490/6	T2 Horizontal	1896	1953	6
S+490/6	T3 Horizontal	1896	1953	6
490/1.5	T1 Vertical	1786	1862	4
490/1.5	T2 Vertical	1808	1855	3
490/1.5	T3 Vertical	1795	1848	2
490/1.5	T1 Horizontal	1863	1898	7
490/1.5	T2 Horizontal	1868	1906	8
490/1.5	T3 Horizontal	1864	1903	7

Table 15. Tensile test of MS1 under different heat treatment conditions – ASTM E8.

Heat treated MS1 Impact toughness at room temperature		
HT Code	Sample	Impact toughness (J)
S+490/6	Vertical	8
S+490/6	Horizontal	13
490/1.5	Vertical	9
490/1.5	Horizontal	19

Table 16. Impact toughness test of MS1 under different heat treatment conditions – ISO 148.

The requirements were not fully met by any of the heat treatments. However, as initially mentioned, additive manufacturing offers several advantages. The DRT deemed the properties achieved with the MS1 alloy heat-treated using the HT 490/1.5 cycle more than sufficient. This treatment avoids the solution annealing step, thereby eliminating its associated costs and technical challenges, while also reducing the tempering time to just 1.5 hours. As a result, it presents a highly competitive solution and a significant improvement over the conventional heat treatment recommended by the powder supplier, at least for this specific application.

Aerospace Application L-PBF

In the case of the material designated for this application, PH17-4 stainless steel, the common heat treatment consists of a solution annealing at elevated temperatures, also above A3, and a precipitation stage (artificial aging it is also call) at medium temperatures. In this case, times and temperatures will define the shape, amount and size of the precipitates that are the main strengthening method of this alloys. To stabilize an initial frame of conditions for the heat treatment, a CALPHAD analysis with the software Thermo-Calc and a literature review [1], [2] & [3] analysis for similar material/technology combinations was carried out and initial candidates for the heat treatment temperatures and times defined.

HT code	Heat treatment applied	HT PH17-4 manufacture via L-PBF HRC (Rockwell C Scale) Hardness
	Def. of Requirements T2.1	35-45
AB	AB (No heat treatment)	40
S+550/4	Solution annealing 1040°C (0.5h) + Aging 550°C (4h)	33
S+480/1	Solution annealing 1040°C (0.5h) + Aging 480°C (1h)	40
460/1	Aging 460°C (1h)	15
650/1	Stress relief 650°C (1h)	23

Table 17. Hardness values for PH17-4 produced by L-PBF under different heat treatment conditions – ISO 6508.

After observing the hardness results, it was evident that in this case, a solution annealing was necessary to achieve the precipitation required in order to increase the material

properties. Both heat treatments that contain a solution annealing step were applied over the tensile and impact test and the samples evaluated.

HT PH17-4 manufacture via L-PBF Tensile test				
HT Code	Sample	Yield Strength (MPa)	UTS (MPa)	Elongation (%)
Def. of Requirements T2.1		1138	1207	12
S+550/4	T1 Vertical	674	1262	11
S+550/4	T2 Vertical	576	1262	10
S+550/4	T3 Vertical	590	1287	11
S+550/4	T1 Horizontal	703	1287	10
S+550/4	T2 Horizontal	651	1285	10
S+550/4	T3 Horizontal	653	1259	12
S+480/1	T1 Vertical	405	1291	15
S+480/1	T2 Vertical	429	1322	11
S+480/1	T3 Vertical	410	1291	12
S+480/1	T1 Horizontal	421	1321	16
S+480/1	T2 Horizontal	461	1348	14
S+480/1	T3 Horizontal	--	--	--

Table 18. Tensile test results of PH17-4 produced by L-PBF under different heat treatment conditions – ASTM E8.

HT PH17-4 manufacture via L-PBF Impact toughness at -50°C		
HT Code	Sample	Impact toughness (J)
S+550/4	Vertical	11
S+550/4	Horizontal	10
S+480/1	Vertical	5
S+480/1	Horizontal	4

Table 19. Impact toughness test results of PH17-4 produced by L-PBF under different heat treatment conditions – ISO 148.

The minimum requirements cannot be achieved with this material and technology, not only in these tensile properties but also in the impact toughness.

Aerospace Application Laser Wire DED

In the case of Laser Wire DED technology, a similar approach was carried out, based on the hardness results, the heat treatment for the tensile and impact test was selected. For this precipitation hardening stainless steel alloy, a combination of CALPHAD analysis and literature review [4], [5] was employed to preselect temperatures and times of the possible heat treatments considering the performance expected of the component and defined in task 2.1.

HT code	Heat treatment applied	HT PH17-4 manufacture via Laser Wire DED HRC (Rockwell C Scale) Hardness
	Def. of Requirements T2.1	35-45
AB	AB (No heat treatment)	32
S+580/4	Solution annealing 1040°C (0.5h) + Aging 580°C (4h)	33
S+550/4	Solution annealing 1040°C (0.5h) + Aging 550°C (4h)	35

S+480/4	Solution annealing 1040°C (0.5h) + Aging 480°C (4h)	40
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Table 20. Hardness values for PH17-4 produced by laser wire DED under different heat treatment conditions – ISO 6508.

Analysing the results, the S+550/4 heat treatment is considered to provide a good balance between hardness (and mechanical strength) while maintaining the ductility required for this application—a key performance characteristic. Consequently, this heat treatment was selected for application to the various wall shapes, with the goal of evaluating their behaviour and ensuring property homogeneity.

HT S+550/4 PH17-4 manufacture via Laser Wire DED Tensile test				
Wall Code	Sample	Yield Strength (MPa)	UTS (MPa)	Elongation (%)
Def. of Requirements T2.1		1138	1207	12
SW	T1	937	992	12
MW	T1 Horizontal	1066	1129	15
MW	T1 Vertical	1039	1114	15
SMW	T1 Horizontal	907	1066	23
SMW	T1 Vertical	957	1039	12

Table 21. Tensile test results of PH17-4 produced by laser wire DED under different heat treatment conditions – ASTM E8.

HT S+550/4 PH17-4 manufacture via Laser Wire DED Impact toughness at -50°C		
HT Code	Sample	Impact toughness (J)
Def. of Requirements T2.1		>32

S+550/4	Vertical	40
S+550/4	Horizontal	38

Table 22. Impact toughness test results of PH17-4 produced by laser wire DED under different heat treatment conditions – ISO 148.

Even though some of the requirements are not achieved, the overall homogeneity of the properties is not a factor of the manufacturing shape or dimensions anymore after heat treatment. Mechanical properties are balancing a bit toward ductility and elongation sacrificing some yield strength and UTS but after analysis by SGC, they are considered sufficient for the application when balanced with the advantages of additive manufacturing.

2.4.2 Classification of typical defects

Additive manufacturing processes are prone to unique defects that can compromise the structural integrity and performance of the final components. Understanding and classifying these defects is a vital step in quality assurance. This section examines the most common defects observed in the produced samples—such as porosity, lack of fusion, and residual stress—and provides insights into their root causes. The classification of defects is divided by technology, been L-PBF the technology selected for the injection mould application and laser wire DED for the aerospace component.

Technology/Material: L-PBF PH17-4

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure

15. Typical defects found on L-PBF technology. (a) magnification x50, (b) magnification x100, (c) magnification x200. All micrographs etched with Vilella's reagent.

In the classification of defects observed in L-PBF technology, the PH17-4 trials are used as a representative example of the typical issues encountered. The accompanying image

highlights two types of defects, marked with blue and yellow arrows, to facilitate their identification and explanation.

The blue arrows indicate porosity resulting from lack of fusion and/or spattering. These defects occur due to insufficient bonding between layers, which can arise from several factors:

- Process parameter issues, such as insufficient energy input in certain areas, leading to incomplete melting.
- Inhomogeneities in the powder layer, where local variations in layer thickness result in uneven fusion. This can stem from raw material issues, such as low powder flowability, or from machine setup problems.
- Spattering, which refers to particle ejections during the laser sintering process. These ejected particles, if not properly removed by the gas flow, can land in unsintered regions of the build bed. If they become oxidized during projection, they can further exacerbate fusion problems.

The yellow arrows identify porosity caused by gas entrapment. This type of defect originates from three main sources:

- Pre-existing gas trapped within the powder particles.
- Gas entrapment during the rapid solidification process.
- Volatilization of certain alloy elements during processing, which subsequently gets trapped in the material.

Mitigating gas porosity requires strict quality control over gas purity, optimized gas flow dynamics, and careful management of process parameters and material composition.

Comparison of Defect Types:

Lack of fusion defects are typically larger and more detrimental than gas porosity. They often present angular shapes, which act as stress concentrators, and are prone to aligning parallel to the build layers. These characteristics significantly compromise the mechanical integrity of the component. Therefore, minimizing lack of fusion defects is a critical priority, particularly those stemming from powder quality and process parameter issues.

In the case of the MS1 alloy manufactured using L-PBF technology, efforts to minimize lack of fusion defects have been implemented, successfully reducing their occurrence to a minimum, as demonstrated in the following micrographs.

Technology/Material: L-PBF MS1

(a)

(b)

Figure 16. Defect-free sample of MS1 produced by L-PBF. (a) magnification x200, (b) magnification x500. All micrographs etched with Vilella's reagent.

The samples manufactured using laser wire DED technology highlight the advantages and challenges of this large-scale, high-productivity process compared to L-PBF. While this technology enables the production of larger parts more efficiently, it comes with specific defect-related challenges when process parameters are not well optimized. Key parameters such as hatch distance (the spacing between centres of two parallel tracks), energy input, and wire feed rate are critical for achieving defect-free samples.

Unlike L-PBF, gas porosity is typically less of a concern in laser wire DED and, when present, constitutes only a small fraction relative to the overall part thickness. However, a common issue is the occurrence of repetitive defects within the same layer or across multiple layers in the same position, which can significantly compromise mechanical properties. Examples of these repetitive lack-of-fusion defects are shown in the following micrographs.

These micrographs, obtained during the implementation process task, were analysed using metallographic preparation and computed tomography (CT) scanning. Both techniques were employed to identify these defects, determine their root causes, and refine the process parameters until defect-free parts were achieved. In the images, blue arrows indicate lack-of-fusion defects, while the red dashed lines illustrate their repetitive nature across different layers.

Technology: Laser Wire DED PH17-4

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 17. Typical defects found on laser wire DED technology. (a) magnification x7, (b) magnification x100, (c) magnification x100. All micrographs at polished state.

Repetitive defects can often arise from misalignments between the infill and contour tracks, which form the strategic path programmed for the robot controlling the laser head. When these parameters are not precisely calibrated for a specific material or part configuration,

such defects are likely to occur. Task 2.2 of the implementation process focused on minimizing these issues, ultimately achieving near defect-free parts produced by laser wire DED using PH17-4 material.

Technology: Laser Wire DED PH17-4

Figure 18. Defect-free sample of PH17-4 produced by laser wire DED technology.

3. Conclusions

This deliverable addresses selection, implementation, testing, and optimization of materials and additive manufacturing (AM) technologies for aerospace and injection moulding applications, with a strong focus on meeting industrial requirements. The objectives include defining and validating requirements for materials, AM processes, and post-processing strategies; selecting suitable materials and technologies; and establishing methodologies for process tuning, heat treatment optimization, and material characterization. All these efforts are directed on producing high-quality AM samples, minimizing defects, improving surface integrity, and enhancing mechanical property homogeneity.

For the injection mould application, MS1 commercial Maraging steel was selected as the optimal material, produced via Laser Powder Bed Fusion (L-PBF). This decision was based on the alloy's capability to meet the mechanical requirements of the application when subjected to the optimized heat treatment, composed of an aging process at 490°C for 1.5 hours (HT 490/1.5). This heat treatment avoids the traditional solution annealing step, reducing associated costs and technical challenges while achieving sufficient mechanical performance and property homogeneity. Special focus was placed on defect analysis during L-PBF processing, with key efforts made to minimize porosity and lack-of-fusion defects.

In parallel, an alternative material, MS1 Lean-Si, was evaluated and relegated to the demonstrator stage. While this composition showed promise in reducing material costs and addressing sustainability goals, issues related to brittleness were identified. These issues are expected to be resolved through further research by ArcelorMittal, enabling its inclusion in future demonstrator tests to assess its viability for the injection mould application.

For the aerospace component, the selected material was PH17-4 precipitation-hardening stainless steel, manufactured using Laser Wire Directed Energy Deposition (DED) technology. This technology, chosen for its scalability and high productivity, was carefully implemented to meet the defined requirements of the specific aerospace application. The focus here was on optimizing process parameters, including hatch distance, energy input, and wire feed rate, to minimize defects such as lack of fusion and ensure consistent mechanical properties across large parts. Repetitive defects, identified through microstructural and CT analysis, were traced back to misalignment issues in the toolpath strategy. These issues were systematically addressed during the implementation process, resulting in near defect-free parts. In addition, after observing the mechanical properties variability related to part shape during manufacturing, it was necessary the design of a specific heat treatments that allow for a reliability in the properties of the material along the whole component and achieving the most suitable balance of properties according to the defined requirements for the application. In this case, a solution annealing at 1040°C for 30 minutes and a posterior quenching in air and precipitation stage at 550°C for 4 hours was selected as the most adequate for the material-technology-application combination.

In summary, this deliverable establishes the consortium's capability to produce samples that meet the requirements for their intended applications in terms of material and manufacturing process. For the injection mould application, the MS1 commercial alloy produced via L-PBF has been validated as the preferred material and process combination, with MS1 Lean-Si slated for further testing at the demonstrator stage once brittleness concerns are resolved. For the aerospace component, the PH17-4 alloy manufactured by laser wire DED has been

successfully implemented, demonstrating its ability to produce high-quality, defect-free parts at scale. With these optimized materials and manufacturing processes in place, the surface integrity of the samples can now be properly evaluated, and machining process characteristics can be analysed, ensuring that the subsequent stages of the project generate realistic and actionable results.

Figure 19. Project state up-to-date with technology and materials selected routes

Next Steps

The samples produced during WP2 will undergo further evaluation in WP3, WP4, and WP5 to build upon the findings presented here. Specifically:

- In WP3, the focus will be on identifying and optimizing machining and finishing processes for AMed samples produced in WP2. This includes analysing the influence of milling, turning, grinding, polishing, and other finishing techniques on surface integrity.

- In WP4, the experimental data generated in the basic characterization in WP2 will be used to calibrate and validate in-house simulation tools. These tools will simulate machining and finishing processes, including milling, turning, and EDM, while accounting for anisotropic material properties, high temperatures, and strain rates.
- In WP5, the AMed and machined components will be comprehensively characterized to assess their surface topography, microstructure, metallurgical features, and mechanical properties. Here again, samples produced in WP2 will be evaluated across the range of characterization techniques proposed.

The knowledge and methodologies developed in WP2, particularly concerning heat treatment optimization, material selection, and additive manufacturing process implementation, will support these upcoming stages in the different WPs. Additionally, the advancements achieved in the task described here in minimizing defects and optimizing manufacturing parameters provide a solid foundation for ensuring consistency, performance, and scalability throughout the project.

4. References

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